

THE USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY GRADES AND THEIR ROLE IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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ANNOTATION

This article describes the processes associated with learning and teaching English in primary grades in our republic, ways to successfully and effectively organize the study of English, taking into account the age-related psychophysiological characteristics of students, and provides information about effective, modern and innovative methods of teaching English in primary grades to increase students' interest in learning the language.

Keywords: Primary grades, teaching English, interesting games, interactive methods, modern innovative technologies, pantomime, modern and innovative methods, young children, communicative.

Introduction. Nowadays, the social order of society in our country has increasingly strengthened the need for teaching foreign languages (English) in primary grades and for communicative purposes. English has been introduced as a subject in primary education, and training of specialists in teaching foreign languages has been established in preschool and primary education. Due to the lack of textbooks that serve to improve the modern goals, content and technologies of teaching English in primary education, and to summarize the traditional and foreign experiences accumulated in the practice of teaching English to primary school students, sufficient efficiency is not achieved in the process of training pedagogical personnel for this area.

There is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our country, which is striving to take its rightful place in the world community today, for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. In particular, in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5117 dated May 19, 2021 “On measures to bring the popularization of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level”, as well as in order to effectively implement

organizational measures to popularize the study of foreign languages, the Cabinet of Ministers decides: In accordance with this resolution, in order to teach foreign languages, mainly English, starting from the primary grades, in all secondary schools, in the form of various interesting games, and at the same time to develop students' oral speech development, and starting from the 2nd grade, the transition to teaching the alphabet, reading and grammar through modern, innovative methods has gradually begun. Today, the ability to know foreign languages has become an integral part of our lives. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, there is a high demand for language learning in them. People initially acquire such knowledge in preschool educational institutions and schools, and later in institutes, training courses or independently learn a foreign language. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and qualifications of teachers. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new material. By combining different methods, the teacher will be able to solve specific educational programs. In teaching English, step-by-step teaching, based on the learner's potential and level, age, gives good results. Psychologists believe that children learn languages faster and more easily than adults.

Recently, the number of people of all ages who are learning English has been increasing significantly. This is because it is becoming increasingly difficult to live without knowing English in the process of life. However, language learning also depends on the age. Scientists have even proven that children learn languages faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong imitation ability, the fact that children have more time than adults, and the fact that they quickly retain the information they learn. Today, it is known that about 60% of the world's population can speak two or more languages. The acceleration of globalization processes in the world, the transition to free market relations, and the encouragement of the introduction of high technologies into production are increasing the need for "linguistic capital", that is, specialists who have perfect command of foreign languages (especially English).

In order to ensure quality and efficiency in foreign language education, the practice of reducing the age of learning/teaching foreign languages is becoming more and more popular. This is due to the widespread concept of "the younger the better / early is better". The decision to include English in the primary education curriculum was

approved based on the following conclusions: Critical Period Hypothesis states that there is a limited developmental period during which it is possible to acquire a language, be it L1 or L2, to normal, nativelike levels. – Critical Period Hypothesis states that there is a limited developmental period during which it is possible to acquire a language, be it L1 or L2, to normal, nativelike levels. As one of the Chinese inventors, Masaru Ibuka, wrote in his famous book "It's Too Late After Three", "...a child's brain can hold an unlimited amount of information...". It should also be noted that children aged 6-7 memorize information mechanically, not understanding its meaning. That is why it is necessary not to start teaching English to primary school students by giving them grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the very first step of teaching a foreign language, it may tire the child and weaken his interest in learning the language. Because teaching a foreign language to primary school students is a difficult and at the same time responsible task. Therefore, the following innovative methods can be used to teach English to primary school students in a meaningful and interesting way: Memorization through sight.

It is known that young children remember objects they see more than what they hear. Therefore, the lesson should be taught through various visual aids, posters, and writing on visible and frequently used objects and objects in everyday life, and making sentences with the new words learned. For example, writing on a book, table, blackboard, pen, window, etc. Since such objects that are often used in everyday life are constantly in sight and are constantly used, the child learns these words involuntarily.

Singing words that are difficult to understand or remember through songs and poems. In this way, along with remembering new words, the child's oral speech also develops. As an example, it can be shown that children learning the English alphabet through singing is more effective than simply memorizing it.

- Competitive grammar and vocabulary learning games include most of them. In this case, children perform various tasks given by the teacher. As a result, competition arises among students, which further increases their interest in learning the language. After all, as Chinese thinkers say: "All human interests arise through competition."

- Mixed techniques - here we can optionally combine different techniques. For example, in this case, children can play games, sing songs, draw pictures, show new words through various actions. The advantage of the technique is diversity. In this case, the student is not limited to only one thing.

- Teaching through cartoons. It is known that children are interested in watching various cartoons. In the process of watching English cartoons, although they do not understand the words in the cartoon, they try to understand the words used by the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

- Learning through interesting games; The role of teaching through various games in teaching English is invaluable. Playing various games during the lesson increases the enthusiasm for learning science in the classroom, encourages even inactive students to participate better in lessons. The following games can be an example of our word.

- "MerryRiddles" Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn words that are unfamiliar to them and find the answer to the riddle.

- "Pantomime". In this, the teacher tells the students a word, and the student shows it. The rest of the students have to find the word and say its English name.

- Learning through the senses (tasting vegetables, fruits, food, touching various objects, smelling flowers). Before learning this new method, it is worth citing the opinion of a practicing psychologist: "A teacher who wants something to be firmly fixed in the memory of children should try to involve as many of the child's senses as possible in the process of memorizing: the eyes, ears, the organ of sound, muscle sensation, and even the organs of smell and taste. "In world linguistics, issues related to medical terms and their use play an important role. Indeed, learning a language through the senses is considered more useful and effective than other methods. For example, a student, after tasting just one apple, knows its color, taste, size, smell, and also says its English name. As a result, when the teacher asks the children the English names of the colors, the children immediately remember the time they ate fruit. Therefore, using such methods helps the student retain the information in their long-term memory.

In conclusion, teaching language to primary school students should not be an obligation, but rather, it should be conducted using interesting games and innovative methods, which can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. Therefore, since the education system also sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we, future teachers, can contribute by developing more perfect ways to effectively use innovative technologies.

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